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**Depression, Meaning in Life and Hope
Among Sedentary and Non-sedentary Older Adults**

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Abstract

Sedentary behaviors among older adults have been found to lead to better overall well-being. This study is a descriptive-comparative research that explored depression, meaning in life and hope among sedentary and non-sedentary older adults. Sixty-nine older adults aged 65 and above consented to participate in a survey. The Beck Depression Inventory – II, the Meaning in Life Scale and the Adult Hope Scale were used to measure the variables. Even amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, results showed that the older adults of this study yielded minimal depressive symptoms, high presence of meaning, average search of meaning and high agency, pathways and overall hope. These results apply for both those with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles. No significant differences were observed for depression, search of meaning, pathways and hope when grouped by lifestyle. Significant differences were noted for presence of meaning and agency with higher scores being observed for those with a sedentary lifestyle. Older adults, regardless of their lifestyle, coped well with their lives, and adjusted to their normal functioning after adversity. The older adults who engage in sedentary and non-sedentary behaviors believed there is meaning in their lives and they actively seek out life's fulfillment and goals. Both sedentary and non-sedentary older adults had agentic thinking and know the pathway achieving their goals. They are generally hopeful and optimistic towards the future. Sedentary behaviors did not create differences in one's tendencies towards depressive symptoms and seemed to foster greater perceived meaning in life and agentic thinking. Recommendations were geared towards fostering active mental processes among older adults.

Keywords: depressive symptoms, agency, pathways, search of meaning, presence of meaning

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Rationale

The number of older adults is significantly increasing worldwide. In a report of World Health Organization-National Institute on Aging and National Institutes of Health (2011), there is an estimated 524 million older adults aged 65 years old and above. They comprise 8% of the world's population. By 2050, projections show that there will be approximately 1.5 billion of their population. In the Philippines, the estimated number of people aged 60 and above as of 2019 is already 9,433,000 while projections show that this will become 23,863,000 in 2050 according to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA). In the province of Nueva Vizcaya, the 2010 census of PSA shows that there are 29,269 older adults aged 60 years old and above.

This growing number of older adults has many implications to society such as socio-cultural, economic, healthcare, and also public policy. The rapidly increasing population of older people will impact on almost all aspects of society (WHO, 2017). Thus, promoting older adults' health and well-being has become a priority for healthy aging among many nations. Halaweh, Ivanoff, Svantesson, and Willen (2018) reported that well-being and physical as well as mental health contribute to healthy aging. Researchers found that healthy aging is affected by numerous factors such as physical and social environments, and behavioral factors. This research intends to focus on depression, meaning in life, and hope as vital factors to healthy aging.

Depression is one of the most common mental health problems globally (Hedayati & Khazaei, 2014). It affects people of all ages including those in old age. According to the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, as cited in Hurley, 2019), the percentage of elderly with depression is between 1% to 5%, however this percentage may be higher since some of the symptoms experienced by this population tend to mimic normal age-related issues. These symptoms may lead to severe consequences like suicide and disability. Therefore, efforts have to be taken to minimize or treat people with depression.

Existing studies indicate several factors that buffer against depression. For instance, Fiske, Wetherell and Gatz (2009) reported that improvements in emotion regulation, use of positive reappraisal, religious involvement and positive self-concepts all protect against depression. However, an aspect that has been linked to depression, but has not yet received enough empirical attention among the elderly population is meaning in life.

Meaning in life pertains to the idea that people are “strongly motivated to find meaning in their lives, to understand the nature of their personal existence and to feel that life is significant and purposeful”. According to Hupkens, Machielse, Goumans and Derkx (2016), finding meaning in life is challenging for older adults. It has been considered as a developmental process that is discovered and created and not something that occurs automatically as a function of age. If meaning in life is to be a useful factor to buffer against depression, then further inquiry into it must be conducted specifically among older adults.

Apart from meaning in life, another factor that can influence depression is hope. According to Gum (2017), hopeful older adults reject negative stereotypes of aging, and they perceive themselves as having good physical, mental and social well-being as well as they envision themselves as aging successfully. However, could this relationship be different among those with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles? This study therefore sought to answer this question in relation to other psychosocial factors like depression and meaning in life. The study explored differences in depression, meaning in life and hope among sedentary and non-sedentary adults. It also provided rich information about the nature of these variables as experienced by older adults. The study is deemed significant because it would yield essential information useful for public policy and promotion of well-being among the aging population of the country.

Statement of Objectives

This study aimed to explore depression, meaning in life, and hope among sedentary and non-sedentary older adults. Specifically, the following questions for answers:

1. What is the level of depression of the older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles?
2. What is the level of meaning in life of the older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles?
3. What is the level of hope of the older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles?
4. Is there a significant difference in depression, meaning in life and hope between older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles?

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

Healthy aging as reported by Halaweh, et. al(2018) is positively influenced by feeling joyous, staying independent, self-possessed contentment, and being financially secured, in addition to being socially engaged and enjoying good physical and mental health. The enhancement of older adults’ physically active lifestyle, social participation, and leisure activities as well as healthy eating habits are all important factors to promote healthy aging. Having a purpose in life and intellectual engagement are also fundamental factors affecting mental health and well-being of older adults. These vital factors are to be considered in developing policies and programs for promoting aging well among older adults.

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm

As shown on Figure 1, this study determined the levels of depression, meaning in life, and hope of respondents. Differences of the levels of depression, meaning in life, and hope of respondents when respondents are grouped according to sedentary and non-sedentary were also determined.

Scope and Delimitation

This study aimed to determine the levels of depression, meaning in life, and hope of the older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles. This study was limited among older adults aged 60 and above who were residing at Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya at the time of the study. The data gathered were limited to the nature of depression, meaning in life, and hope among sedentary and non-sedentary older adults. The data gathering procedures were limited to the use of survey questionnaires floated from February to June. Quantitative data gathered were only used to interpret the results of the study.

Significance of the Study

The study, which aimed at determining the levels of depression, meaning in life, and hope among older adults in relation to their health, are significant to the following:

Aged Community. The results of the study provides information that could serve as points of reflection among older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles towards participating to healthy aging programs and activities for older adults of the municipality of Bayombong.

Policymakers. This study provides a baseline survey data that would help policymakers craft policies for the general well-being of the aging community.

Social Workers. The results on the determination of the levels of depression, meaning in life, and hope in this study would allow social workers to craft programs to address the problems on depression, finding meaning in life, and hope among older adults.

Psychologists. This study would help psychologists design relevant interventions to aid the older adults for a successful and healthy aging.

Future Researchers. This study is limited to three variables particularly depression, meaning in life, and hope. Hence, future researchers could explore other possible factors affecting healthy aging among older adults.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are conceptually and operationally defined in this study:

Depression refers to the feelings of sadness and/or a loss of interest in activities once enjoyed (American Psychiatric Association, 2018). In this study, the Beck Depression Inventory questionnaire was used to assess depression.

Health status refers to the actual health condition of the respondents. It is measured in terms of level of difficulty.

Healthy aging refers to the process of developing and maintaining the functional ability that enables well-being in old age (WHO).

Hope refers to the perceived capability to derive pathways to desired goals, and motivate oneself via agency thinking to use those pathways (Snyder, 2002). In this study, the Adult Hope Scale by Snyder was used to assess hope.

Meaning in life refers to the individual perception, understanding or belief on the value and importance of one's own life and activities. In this study, the Steger questionnaire was used to assess meaning in life.

Non-sedentary adults are older people characterized as physically active and socially participative as well as engaging in activities. These are older adults who sit less than 5 hours a day.

Older adults refer to individuals who are aged 60 years old and above.

Sedentary adults are older people who are the exact opposites of non-sedentary adults. Their characteristics are physically inactive, socially non-participative, and disengaging in activities. These people are those who sit greater than or equal to 5 hours a day.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Depression

According to the American Psychiatric Association (2019), depression is a common and serious mental disorder that is treatable. It leads to feelings of sadness, loss of interest in activities once enjoyed, decline in a person's ability to function, difficulty in concentrating, loss of energy, and thoughts of death or suicide. The National Institute of Mental Health (NIHM, 2019) outlined three forms of depression: major depression, persistent depressive disorder or dysthymia and minor depression. However, Krans (2017) used the term "geriatric" depression for the mental and emotional disorder affecting older adults, and it falls under *subsyndromal* depression indicating that among older adults, the full criteria for a major depression is not often met. For all types, depressive symptoms should have been present for at least two weeks because any diagnosis is made.

Yoshida, Iwasa, Kumagai, Suzuki, Awata and Yoshida (2015) reported a 16.9% prevalence rate of depression among their sample of 65 year old Japanese community members. A higher prevalence rate however was noted by Oro-Josef, dela Cruz and Salandan (2011) in their sample of Filipino older adults with 26.5% of the 196 elderly having depressive symptoms. Nonetheless, according to Fiske, Wetherell and Gatz (2009), depression is less prevalent among older adults than in younger adults but it has more serious consequences to the individual. Among older adults, depression is linked with an increased risk of death, disability, cognitive impairment and dementia. There is also a higher risk of suicide with a greater likelihood to complete suicide compared to younger adults (Rodda, Walker, & Carter, 2011). The symptoms of depression appear to mimic normal characteristics of aging, but depression is not a normal part of aging. A self-critical thinking thought pattern also has been reported to exacerbate and maintain a depressed state (Fiske et al., 2009).

Some people are at higher risk of developing depression than others. These risk factors include being female, having a chronic medical illness like cancer, diabetes or heart disease, have a disability, poor sleep and are lonely or socially isolated. Moreover, those with a personal or family history of depression, misuse alcohol or drugs or experienced stressful events such as loss of a spouse, or marital separation also increase one's risk of developing depression.

Depression is treatable. Existing studies have documented how depression can be managed using certain intervention programs with program efficacy being as effective for older adults as it is for younger adults (Rodda et al., 2011). For instance, Blake, Mo and Thomas (2009) documented how physical exercise can reduce clinical depression among older adults. In their review of eleven randomized controlled trials, they found efficacy of physical exercise in reducing depression in nine studies, at least in terms of short-term positive outcomes. This was confirmed by Kok and Reynolds (2017) in their study when they emphasized how psychological therapies and exercise can be effective for mild to moderate depression. Generally, psychological and drug treatment is effective with selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRI) as the first line of pharmacological treatment for most older adults. Management of depression using psychosocial strategies also prevents further deterioration among older patients (Rodda et al., 2011). Fiske et al. (2009) also reported that preventive interventions for depression among older adults including "behavioral activation, cognitive restructuring, problem-solving skills training, group support and life review".

Indeed, exercise is an important factor that buffer against depression in late life. Wrosch, Schulz, Miller, Lupien and Dunne (as cited in Fiske et al., 2009) reported that engaging in active behaviors such as physical exercise not only reduced depressive symptoms but also reduced the secretion of the stress hormone. Other forms of exercise such as aerobics (Sjösten & Kivelä, as cited in Fiske et al., 2009) and weight training (Singh et al., as cited in Fiske et al., 2009) have also been shown as effective anti-depressants. Furthermore, Motl et al. (as cited in Fiske et al., 2009) found that there are lower relapse rates for depression among those who continue to exercise. However, a noteworthy aspect of exercise that has to be clarified is its definition among participants. For instance, in the study of Ceria-Ulep, Serafica and Tse (2011) among Filipino older adults in Hawaii, it was noted that exercise was viewed as a proxy measure of physical activity. Their study emphasize how certain forms of activities such as walking, gardening, doing household chores, walking kids to school, cleaning the car and garage as well as walking around the house, while considered as non-sedentary behaviors, were already forms of exercise among these older adults. This study therefore emphasized the importance of clarifying definition of exercise among this age group.

Depression is a true and treatable medical condition, not a normal part of aging (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2017). Depression is often not well recognized or detected in older people. One in six women and one in eight men will experience depression at some stage of their lives. The precise rates of depression in older people are not yet known. However, it is thought that between 10 and 15 per cent of Australians over the age of 65 experience depression. Rates of depression among people living in residential aged care facilities are believed to be much higher than the general population – around 35 per cent. Depression can reduce a person's quality of life and their relationships with friends and family. Severe depression is a risk factor for suicidal thoughts and suicide can be life threatening. Among males, the highest suicide rate in the population is among those aged 85 and older (Department of Health and Human Services, 2018).

Han et al. (2015) found, through stepwise regression analysis, that healthy aging was significantly influenced by depression. Considering the correlation between depression and healthy aging, the former was significantly correlated to the latter. Moreover, depression was a more influential psychological factor in healthy aging. They have stated that not only physical health and mental health is very important to healthy aging and the life of old people.

Gulich, Duro and Cesar (2016) assessed the prevalence of depression and associated factors among Brazilian elderly in Arroio Trinta, Southern Brazil. During home visits, a questionnaire was administered to all people aged 60 or older living in the municipality in 2013. The Geriatric Depression Scale Short Form (GDS-15) was used. The χ^2 test was performed to compare proportions and Poisson regression with robust adjustment of variance in the multivariate analysis. The effect measure applied was the prevalence ratio. The prevalence of depression among 552 (out of 568) elderly studied was 20.4% (95%CI 17.3 - 23.8). An adjusted analysis conducted according to a predefined hierarchical model showed higher prevalence ratios of depression among females, single people, those with lower household income, smokers, and those who had been hospitalized in the 12 months preceding the interview. Engaging in leisure-time activities such as dances and religious activities or regular physical activity were protective factors for depression. Results from this study demonstrate the need of proper treatment and management of this condition at the community level.

Mina (2017) found out the debilitating factors causing the increase in the prevalence of depression and to seek the nurses' role in prevention and treatment of depression among aged population. The methodology of this study was a literature review and 12 articles have been reviewed. Inductive content analysis has been used for this study. The result of the study suggests that the prevalence of depression is on the increase due to lack of social support, divorce, alcoholism, smoking tobacco, lack of physical activity and exercise, stress, conflicts between old and new values etc. It also indicates that nurses play a vital role in reducing depression by encouraging social support, using Interventions for Depression Improvements (INDI) model, involving family members, initiating collaborative care, development of a good nurse-patient relationship, promotion of positivism, encouragement of physical exercises, patient education and creating of self-awareness among elderly patients. The study recommends that the implementation of nonmedication treatment must be given a more prominent stand in the treatment of depression.

Sivertsen, Bjorklof, Engedal, Selbaek and Helvik (2015) stated that depression is a prevalent and disabling condition in older persons, 60 years and over, that increases the risk of mortality and negatively influences quality of life (QOL). The relationship between depression, or depressive symptoms, and QOL has been increasingly addressed by research in recent years, but a review that can contribute to a better understanding of this relationship in older persons is lacking. Sivertsen et al. (2015) found that depressed older persons had poorer global and generic health-related QOL than nondepressed individuals. An increase in depression severity was associated with a poorer global and generic health-related QOL. The associations appeared to be stable over time and independent of how QOL was assessed. This review found a significant association between severity of depression and poorer QOL in older persons, and the association was found to be stable over time, regardless which assessment instruments for QOL were applied. The lack of a definition of the multidimensional and multilevel concept QOL was common, and the large variety of QOL instruments in various studies make a direct comparison between the studies difficult.

According to Fiske, Wetherell and Gatz (2010), depression is less prevalent among older adults than among younger adults but can have serious consequences. Over half of cases represent a first onset in later life. Although suicide rates in the elderly are declining, they are still higher than in younger adults and more closely associated with depression. Depressed older adults are less likely to endorse affective symptoms and more likely to display cognitive changes, somatic symptoms, and loss of interest than are younger adults. Risk factors leading to the development of late life depression likely comprise complex

interactions among genetic vulnerabilities, cognitive diathesis, age-associated neurobiological changes, and stressful events. Insomnia is an often overlooked risk factor for late life depression. It is suggested that a common pathway to depression in older adults, regardless of which predisposing risks are most prominent, may be curtailment of daily activities. Accompanying self-critical thinking may exacerbate and maintain a depressed state. Offsetting the increasing prevalence of certain risk factors in late life are age-related increases in psychological resilience. Other protective factors include higher education and socioeconomic status, engagement in valued activities, and religious or spiritual involvement. Treatments including behavioral therapy, cognitive behavioral therapy, cognitive bibliotherapy, problem-solving therapy, brief psychodynamic therapy, and life review/reminiscence therapy are effective but too infrequently used with older adults. Preventive interventions including education for individuals with chronic illness, behavioral activation, cognitive restructuring, problem-solving skills training, group support, and life review have also received support.

Meaning in life

Martela and Steger (2016) defined meaning in life in terms of three concepts: coherence, purpose and significance. According to them, coherence pertains to a sense of comprehensibility and one's life making sense. Purpose means having a sense of goal, aim and direction in life, whereas significance is the sense of one's life having value and worth.

A sense of meaning is a cognizance of order, coherence, and purpose in one's existence, the pursuit and attainment of worthwhile goals, and an accompanying sense of fulfillment (Reker, 2000). As explained by Berger and Pullberg (1965), behavior is not determined by an objective sense of meaning. Instead, that behavior arises from subjective meanings that are developed by the individual. They stated that meaning is a subjective phenomenon that is created jointly during the process of social interaction.

The study of Krause (2009) indicated that older adults who have a strong sense of meaning in life are less likely to die over the course of the follow-up period than older people who do not have a strong sense of meaning in their lives. This finding is noteworthy because it represents for the first time that meaning in life has been linked with mortality in a nationally representative sample of older people. Second, the results reveal that the effects of meaning on mortality are mediated by physical health. More specifically, the findings suggest that greater meaning is associated with better health, and better health is, in turn, associated with a lower risk of dying during the study follow-up period. This finding is important for the following reason: Some investigators use health as a control variable in studies of mortality—it is something that is removed statistically in order to demonstrate the effects of constructs that are of greater interest. But researchers who rely on this practice may be selling their studies short if the effects of their core constructs, like meaning in life, are also related to health. The third main finding from this study has to do with having a sense of purpose in life. More specifically, the data suggest that having a sense of purpose may be more consequential than the three other dimensions of meaning that were evaluated in the present study.

A number of studies suggest that a strong sense of meaning in life is associated with better physical health (Krause, 2009), better mental health (Reker, 2000), and there appears to be only one study that empirically evaluates the relationship between meaning in life and mortality (O'Connor & Vallerand, 1998). With regard to the relationship between meaning in life and mortality, O'Connor and Vallerand (1998) found out that at the bivariate level, a stronger sense of meaning in life is associated with a lower mortality risk. However, they went on to report that the relationship between meaning and mortality is no longer statistically significant once the effects of age, sex, and self-rated health have been added to the model. Taken as a whole, the results provided by O'Connor and Vallerand (1998) appear to suggest that meaning in life plays a relatively inconsequential role in determining mortality.

People generally strive to live meaningful lives. In recent years, the concept of meaning in life (MIL) internationally has gained attention in society and in healthcare settings. MIL is considered essential for 'a good life' (Derckx, 2011; Esfahani Smith, 2017). MIL is important for nurses because of its positive association with health (Ryff, 2012; Steger, 2012), well-being (Steger, 2012); and quality of life (Pitkala, Laakkonen, Strandberg, and Tilvis, 2004). However, MIL is not only a means to an end, it is important on its own merits (Derckx, 2011; Esfahani Smith, 2017). MIL is a comprehensive dynamic construct, as the description of Brandstätter Baumann, Borasio and Fegg (2012) explains:

'Meaning in life is a highly individual perception, understanding or belief about one's own life and activities and the value and importance ascribed to them. Meaning and purpose are related to terms like order, fairness, coherence, values, faith and belonging... Meaning

in life comprises the engagement in or commitment to goals or a life framework and the subsequent sense of fulfilment and satisfaction or lack thereof.'

As explained by Berger and Pullberg (1965), behavior is not determined by an objective sense of meaning. Instead, that behavior arises from subjective meanings that are developed by the individual. They stated that meaning is a subjective phenomenon that is created jointly during the process of social interaction.

According to Hupkens, Machielse, Goumans and Derkx (2016), finding meaning in life is challenging for older adults. It has been considered as a developmental process that is discovered and created and not something that occurs automatically as a function of age. As Frankl (1905-1997) a concentration camp survivor formed his theory about "man's will to find meaning" prior to World War II. Frankl observed in the concentration camp that life has meaning under all conditions and that people have both the capacity and ability to find meaning in their lives. Everything can be taken from a human except the freedom to choose one's attitude in every situation. It is how a person transforms the situation from tragedy into achievement that matters (Frankl, 1959). Meaning can be attained through creative, experimental and attitudinal values. Creative values inspire individuals to create, produce and achieve purpose in life through some form of work. Experimental values of importance for purpose in life include positive experiences such as love. Attitudinal values include how a person chooses her/his stance towards unavoidable, negative conditions. If a person is obstructed in the finding of meaning feelings of meaninglessness can occur. Frankl (1962) defines such feelings as an "existential vacuum", described as a state of emptiness manifested in boredom, which can lead to anxiety and depression.

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Hope

In Snyder's (2000) Hope Theory, hope was defined as "a positive motivational state that is based on an interactively derived sense of successful (a) agency and (b) pathways. Agency refers to the sense of having goals that are valuable and uncertain and provide direction and an endpoint for hopeful thinking. Pathways pertain to the path one takes to reach desired goals and the ability to produce this path (Snyder, 2000).

According to Snyder (2000), individuals with high hope view barriers as challenges they need to surmount and use their pathway thoughts to plan alternative routes towards their goals. Moreover, those with high hope also tend to have higher academic achievement, and lower depressive symptoms.

Among older adults, some life events (e.g. poor health, death of a spouse, or financial difficulties after retirement) may lead them to have difficulty in pursuing goals or being hopeful. However, existing studies indicate the importance of hope among older adults emphasizing how it can lead to positive outcomes. For instance, Gum (2018) found that older adults tend to cast off negative stereotypes about

aging; views themselves as aging successfully, cope well with stressors and generally have good physical, mental and social well-being. Haase et al. (as cited in Gum, 2018) clarified the mechanism by which goals influence the level of hope among older adults by explaining that older adults “actively think about, select, and pursue goals, and they also stop pursuing other goals, which is adaptive in certain situations”.

Hope also influences older adults’ resilience. In the study of Polson, Gillespie and Myers (2018), “hope was found as a strong and significant predictor of resilience among older adults and that hope tends to mediate the effect of spiritual experience on resilience”. The researchers conducted the study among community-dwelling or urban older adults in the U.S. who were living with physical, emotional and social issues including poverty, social isolation and poor health. Polson et al. (2018) found that “more than social connection or physical ability, hope predicted whether at-risk, older adults exhibited resilience”. Furthermore, they found that agency and pathway, two features of hope, are spiritually driven, and integrating spirituality in hope-based interventions among older adults can impact their well-being.

In another study among older adults, Ferguson, Taylor and McMahon (2017) found that “high hope was significantly associated with high positive affect, and high meaning in life; and high experiential avoidance was associated with high negative affect and low meaning in life”. The study was conducted among 259 older adults aged 65 to 94 years old. Overall, Ferguson et al. (2017) confirmed existing studies that hope leads to a feeling that one can achieve future goals, which in turn leads to greater happiness, a sense of purpose and meaning in life.

In a 2016 study by Krause, Pargament and Ironson, the importance of hope among older adults was revealed. Using data from the Landmark Spirituality and Health Survey, Krause et al (2016) surveyed a nationally representative sample of adults 18 years and older in the US on death anxiety, religious hope, and general hope. It was found that hope, specifically religious sense of hope, lessens death anxiety across successively older age groups. This implies that older adults who have a religiously-oriented sense of hope will likely have fewer symptoms of general anxiety and less likely to develop anxiety disorders.

Hopelessness is a core feature of depression; therefore individuals who have a lowered sense of hope can be expected to have more depressive symptoms. Assari and Lankarani (2016) sought out to confirm this in a national sample of White and Black older adults in the US more than 65 years old. The study’s sample included Christians and those who never had associations with any faith. Their findings found evidence for this hypothesis indicating that higher depressive symptoms were predictive of hopelessness. Furthermore, their study showed that compared to White older adults, the association between depressive symptoms and hopelessness was weaker for the Blacks. Overall, the study underscored that depressive symptoms accompany more hopelessness among White or Caucasians older adults compared to African-American or Black sample of older adults.

Minimizing hopelessness or increasing hope in older adults in an important endeavor particularly that late adulthood brings with it anxiety-provoking aspects such as death, aging and poor physical health. This was what Kim (2019) sought out to in her dissertation. By employing data from the Health and Retirement Study and Complicated Grief Treatment in Older Adults Study, Kim (2019) examined how positive emotions such as hope can impact bereavement adjustment among widowed older adults. Her study found that hope can improve complicated grief interventions and is associated with resolution of complicated grief symptoms. Promoting hope as a person increasing age is also very important since, as Marquesa and Gallagher (2017) found, hope appear to be higher in the young and middle adulthood age group and lowest in the oldest age group.

In another study, hope was explored in relation to other positive psychology concepts such as positive affect and meaning in life. Ferguson, Taylor and McMahon (2017) showed that high hope was related to high positive affect and high meaning in life. The study revealed how hope for the future can contribute to well-being, enhanced positive aging and increased meaningfulness in life among older adults.

Sedentary and Non-sedentary Older Adults

Aging is a natural process which all humans undergo. The physiological changes associated with aging can, however, be delayed with proper intervention strategies like balance training, and strength training programs which increase balance, flexibility and endurance among older adults (Kaur & Sharma, 2017). In the 2017 study of Kaur and Sharma, active and sedentary older adults were compared in terms of physical performances. Results showed that “active older adults are more physically fit and have better balance than sedentary older adults”. The study highlighted the importance of physical activity or a non-

sedentary lifestyle to improve activities of daily living and decrease the risk for metabolic disorder such as diabetes, hypertension, musculoskeletal disorders and obesity among older adults.

The same results were found in Po-Wen, Fox, Yung, Wen-Jung and Li-jung (2016) in their study among community-dwelling older adults in Taiwan. Regression analysis showed that moderate to vigorous physical activity was linked with higher follow-up general and specific dimensions of well-being. Furthermore, Po-Wen et al. (2016) found that light physical activity was a significant predictor of psychological growth and social well-being. Overall, their study provided evidence that light, moderate and vigorous physical activity among older adults make distinct contributions to their well-being.

Indeed, physical activity is important for older adults. Gomez, Gomez, Artalejo and Esquinas (2017) stressed this when they found that sedentary behaviors like watching TV led to higher depressive symptoms among older adults. The effects were particularly significant among women who were found to have spent more time watching TV and less time in other sedentary behaviors like reading and using the computer. In their study, those who engaged in more sedentary behavior also had higher psychological distress at follow-up. This is similar to the results of Yoshida et al. (2015) in their sample of Japanese older adults from northern Japan which showed that continuous physical activity, therefore non-sedentary lifestyle such as “calisthenics, going for walks, gate-ball, jogging, tennis, golf, hiking, dancing, swimming, walking, and martial arts” reduced the incidence of depressive symptoms in their 3-year follow-up.

Synthesis

Globally, depression is a mental health concern that affects everyone regardless of age. Older adults are not exempted. And while the prevalence of depression is lower among older adults, its effect in this special population can be more serious than to younger populations. Specific interventions therefore have to be crafted to ensure that older adults in one’s community can be prevented or helped in managing depression. Apart from this, hope interventions also seem to promote well-being among older adults. Most studies highlighted how it can lead to resilience and general well-being and therefore as a useful buffer against age-related stressors among older adults. Sadly, most studies conducted about hope in old age were done in Western countries. Studies therefore have to be conducted in the local setting.

Furthermore, physical activity among the elderly population has consistently shown to promote well-being. But there appears to be a knowledge gap on the definition of physical activity or non-sedentary behavior; hence, further studies have to be conducted in this area. Some studies differentiate between sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles with the latter being associated with better overall health. In consideration of these, this study will focus on assessing depression, meaning in life and hope among older adults and discovering distinctions between those with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles.

Chapter 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative approach specifically using descriptive-comparative research design. In this approach, data about older adults’ depression, meaning in life and hope were gathered using questionnaires and the compared by sedentary or non-sedentary lifestyles.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Bayombong which is a first class municipality of Nueva Vizcaya and the seat of the provincial capital of the province.

Research Instrument

This study employed demographic questionnaire, a depression scale, a meaning in life scale and an adult hope scale. Specifically, the demographic questionnaire contained basic information about the older adults to include daily activities, ages, sex, etc.

The Beck Depression Inventory – II (BDI-II) is a 21-item self-report inventory that measures the severity of depressive symptoms based on the diagnostic criteria of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) – IV. It has been designed to assess depression in adults and adolescents aged 13 years old and over. The BDI is a paper and pencil questionnaire that takes approximately 5 minutes to complete. Respondents answered the items on a 4-point Likert scale from 0 to 3. Total scores ranged from

0-63 with lower scores representing fewer depressive symptoms. Reliability of the scale has been developed based on clinical samples and college students. Internal consistency yielded a Cronbach's alpha of .92 for the outpatients and .93 for the college sample (Community-University Partnership for the Study of Children, Youth and Families, 2011). To improve reliability, the questionnaire was translated in Filipino and validated by experts.

The Meaning in Life Questionnaire by Steger, Frazier, Oishi and Kaler (2006) is a 10-item scale designed to assess two dimensions of meaning in life: presence of meaning, and search for meaning. Respondents answered each item on a 7-point Likert scale with 1 as absolutely true to 7 as absolutely untrue. In scoring the MLQ, item 9 was reverse scored. Items 1, 4, 5, 6, and 9 were summed to make up the presence of meaning subscale and the rest of the items make the search for meaning subscale.

The Adult Hope Scale (AHS) by Snyder, Harris, Anderson, Holleran, Irving, Sigmon, et al. (1991) is a 12-item measure of a person's level of hope. It comprises of two subscales: agency and pathways. Of the 12 items, 4 make up the Agency subscale and 4 make up the Pathways subscale. The remaining 4 items are fillers. Each item was answered using an 8-point Likert-type scale ranging from Definitely False to Definitely True. It should be noted that the authors recommend that when administering the scale, it is called "The Future Scale". Items 2, 9, 10, and 12 make up the agency subscale. Items 1, 4, 6, and 8 make up the pathway subscale. Researchers can either examine results at the subscale level or combine the two subscales to create a total hope score.

Sampling Procedure and Respondents of the Study

Respondents of this study were 69 older adults aged 60 and above. Respondents were categorized into sedentary or non-sedentary depending on their time spent sitting as part of daily leisure. Those who sit greater than or equal to 5 hours a day were considered as sedentary whereas those who sit less than 5 hours a day were considered non-sedentary. Shown on Table 1 is the distribution of respondents by lifestyle, sex and age:

Table 1.

Respondent Distribution by Lifestyle, Sex and Age

Profile	Sedentary		Non-sedentary		Total		
	f	%	f	%	f	%by profile	
Sex	Male	9	52.90	8	47.10	17	24.64
	Female	31	59.60	21	40.40	52	75.36
Age	60-65 years old	14	46.70	16	53.30	30	43.48
	66-70 years old	10	50.00	10	50.00	20	28.99
	71 and above	16	84.20	3	15.80	19	27.53
Total		40	58.00	29	42.00	69	100

As shown above, respondents of the study are mostly female (75%) and belonging to the 60-65 year old age group (43.48%). Fifty-eight percent are sedentary individuals, which indicate that they sit for more than 5 hours in a day, and are not generally living an active lifestyle.

Data Gathering Procedures

Respondents were purposively selected based on their age and lifestyles. Once identified, an informed consent form was provided to them. This form contained the nature of the study and their willingness to be part of it. Questionnaires were distributed, and collected after answering.

Analysis of Data

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the level of depression, meaning in life and hope of the participants. Differences in these variables by lifestyle were analyzed using independent samples t-test. To interpret the scores for the Depression Scale, the following descriptions were used: 0-13 = minimal (depressive symptoms); 14-29 = mild; 20-28 = moderate; and 29-63 = severe. To interpret scores for the Meaning in Life Scale, the following interpretation was used: 1.00-1.49 = Very Low; 1.50-2.49 = Low; 2.50-5.49 = Average; 5.50-6.49 = High; 6.50-7.00 = Very High with higher scores indicating higher meaning in life. To interpret the scores for the Hop Scale, the following qualitative descriptions were used: 1.00-1.49 = Very Low; 1.50-3.49 = Low; 3.50-5.49 = Average; 5.50-7.49 = High; 7.50-8.00 = Very High.

Chapter 4

PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This section is divided into four parts with the first three focusing on older adults' level of depression, meaning in life and hope by lifestyle, and the last section presenting differences in these three variables in terms of sedentary or non-sedentary lifestyles.

Section 1: Level of Depression of Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Table 2.

Level of Depression between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Depression	Sedentary			Non-sedentary			Total		
	f	% by depression level	% by lifestyle	f	% by depression level	% by lifestyle	f	% by depression level	% by lifestyle
Minimal	36	59.00	90.00	25	41.00	86.20	61	100.00	88.40
Mild	4	80.00	10.00	1	20.00	3.40	5	100.00	7.20
Moderate	0	0.00	0.00	1	100.00	3.40	1	100.00	1.40
Severe	0	0.00	0.00	2	100.00	6.90	2	100.00	2.90
Total	40	58.00	100.00	29	42.00	100.00	69	100.00	100.00

Table 2 shows that 88% of the older adults have minimal depressive symptoms regardless of lifestyle. This indicates that these older adults experience occasional feelings of sadness or loneliness, as with most other individuals. Their emotions are within their control and do not create disabling effects on their well-being. The changes or stressful life events brought about by getting older such as death of loved ones, medical concerns or retirement may make older adults stressed, sad or lonely, but eventually, they are able to cope and return back to their normal functioning.

There are however 8 individuals or 11.59% who yielded mild (n=5), moderate (n=1) and severe (2) depressive symptoms. Unlike those with minimal depressive symptoms, these individuals experience a medical condition that interferes with their daily functioning. The symptoms they experience may take the form of persistent sadness, loss of interest in usual activities that give one meaning or pleasure, hopelessness, helplessness, restlessness, guilt, decreased energy, difficulty in sleeping, concentrating, suicide ideations, or attempts, and other aches or pains that do not ease even with treatment (National Institute of Mental Health, 2019).

The current findings differ from the results of Valentin, Aguirre, Ante, Calderon, Cunanan, Lim, ... and Quilala (2015) that indicated that as much as 31% Filipino older adults have depressive symptoms. Although it must be pointed out that in Valentin et al.'s (2015) study, almost all except for one are females. It also differs from Oro-Josef, dela Cruz and Salandanan's (2011) study of Filipino elderly which reported a 6.6 prevalence rate of depression. This was anticipated since prevalence rates differ depending not only on age but on factors like nationality, sex, and socio-economic status.

The current study's results show that depression is infrequent suggesting that older adults remain to have good mental health. This is surprising since at the time of the study, the province was on community quarantine due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Most people are not allowed to leave their homes, and do basic things particularly the elderly who are most prone to the virus. Physical distancing is enforced and day-to-day activities are disrupted. These in turn limit or prevent social connectedness (Buenaventura, Ho & Lapid, 2020). Avashi and Grover (as cited in Buenaventura et al., 2020) stated that prolonged confinement may lead the elderly to be lonely, to have declined cognitions, and disrupted sleeping patterns. Furthermore, the lack of social engagements may intensify stress and reduce coping skills which increase older adults' risk for the development of depression.

However, given the results, it may be implied that the respondents, amidst the COVID-19 risks, have good protective factors. This may be assumed to be in the form of family support, adequate finances, and low genetic tendencies for depression. Esteban (as cited in Buenaventura et al., 2020) stated that Filipino cultural practices also seem to buffer against risks to well-being and this includes religious practices, one's faith and spirituality. Since the study was focused only on discovering older adults' levels of depression, it is unclear as to what may have led to the older adults' minimal depressive symptoms. Further research may therefore explore on the factors that contribute to low or minimal depression, particularly during the COVID-19 crisis.

Moreover, Table 2 shows that by lifestyle, four older adults with sedentary lifestyle yielded minimal depressive symptoms, whereas two non-sedentary adult reported minimal symptoms, one

moderate, and one several depressive symptoms. This was unexpected since the study is built on an assumption that sedentary behaviors protect against depression as based on existing research. However, Huang, Li, Gan, Wang, Jiang, Cao and Lu (2020) reported that the relationship of sedentary behaviors and depression may in fact be inconsistent. In their study, they found that sedentary behaviors was positively associated with clinical depression, with mentally passive sedentary behaviors such as watching TV as one of the factors that increase risk for depression. On the other hand, mentally active sedentary behaviors, such as using a computer, were unrelated to depression risks. This was supported by Hamer and Stamatakis (2014) who found that sedentary behaviors that involved mental processes like using the internet and reading were associated with lower depressive symptoms. They also found that among older adults, using computers for greater than an hour a day led to a better verbal memory and executive functioning compared with non-users. These findings highlight the need to specify actual sedentary behaviors engaged in by older adults to get a clearer idea of how depression or other mental health outcomes may occur due to specific lifestyles.

Section 2: Level of Meaning in Life between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Table 3.

Level of Meaning in Life between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Meaning in Life	Lifestyle	N	Mean	SD	QD
Presence of meaning	Sedentary	40	6.23	.79	High
	Non-Sedentary	29	5.57	1.04	High
Search of meaning	Sedentary	40	5.02	1.45	Average
	Non-Sedentary	29	5.00	1.19	Average

*Legend: 1.00-1.49 = Very Low; 1.50-2.49 = Low; 2.50-5.49 = Average; 5.50-6.49 = High; 6.50-7.00 = Very High

The table above indicates that respondents of the study yielded high scores for presence in meaning and average scores in search of meaning. Presence of meaning pertains to one's sense of goal and overall direction in life (Martela & Stager, 2016). Having high scores indicate that older adults feel strongly that there is meaning in their lives and that they are aware where they are heading to. Search of meaning, according to Reker (2000), refers to the awareness of order, coherence and purpose in one's existence. Older adults of this study yielded average scores in this area indicating that they are pursuing worthwhile goals and have a sense of fulfillment in their lives. For both dimensions, those with sedentary lifestyles yielded higher mean scores (M=6.23 and 5.02 respectively) compared to the non-sedentary group.

According to Hupkens et al. (2016), meaning in life among older adults is different from the younger generation. For older adults, finding meaning in life is a challenging developmental process that is attained through creating and discovering connections with self and others (Hupkens, Machiels, Goumans, & Derkx, 2016). Krause (2004) explained that life's meaning becomes increasingly important as people age. Drawing on Erikson's theory, Krause (2004) argued that meaning in life may be achieved when the older adult reconciles what he/she set out to do in life and what he/she has actually achieved. If the crisis was not resolved, then the older adult slips into despair. Basing on the results on the table above, it would appear that the older adults of the study, regardless of lifestyle, are able to attain meaning in their lives, as evidenced by a high presence of meaning and average tendencies for actively seeking out meaning in their lives.

Section 3: Level of Hope between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Table 4.

Level of Hope between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Hope	Lifestyle	N	Mean	SD	QD
Agency	Sedentary	40	6.80	0.83	High
	Non-Sedentary	29	6.11	1.25	High
Pathway	Sedentary	40	6.71	1.13	High
	Non-Sedentary	29	6.21	1.21	High
Total Hope	Sedentary	40	5.97	0.69	High
	Non-Sedentary	29	5.73	0.90	High

*Legend: 1.00-1.49 = Very Low; 1.50-3.49 = Low; 3.50-5.49 = Average; 5.50-7.49 = High; 7.50-8.00 = Very High

Results shown on the table above indicate that older adults with a sedentary lifestyle yielded higher mean scores for agency (M=6.80), pathway (6.71) and for overall hope score (M=5.97). Nonetheless, both groups yielded high mean scores for the two subscales and for the overall hope score. These results show that older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles have acknowledge that they have valuable goals which point them to toward hopeful thinking and they know which paths to take to attain these desired goals. Having high hope among older adults signify that they view themselves as aging successfully, can cope with stressors associated with normal aging, and can generally attain physical, mental and social well-being.

Hirsch, Sirois and Lyness (2011) examined hope and its subscales as possible moderators of the relationship between functional impairment and depressive symptoms among older adults. They found that older adults with functional impairment benefits from agency and pathways. It may be implied therefore that because the respondents of the study score high in all areas of the hope scale, they will benefit from being hopeful and having self-efficacy or agency and may be protected from developing depressive symptoms.

Section 4: Differences in Depression, Meaning in Life and Hope between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Table 5.

Differences in Level of Depression between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Lifestyle	N	Mean	SD	QD	t	df	Sig.
Sedentary	40	7.43	5.09	Minimal	-.233	67	.817
Non-Sedentary	29	7.83	9.17	Minimal			

*Legend: 0-13 = Minimal (depressive symptoms); 14-29 = Mild; 20-28 = Moderate; and 29-63 = Severe

The table above shows individuals with non-sedentary lifestyle (M=7.83) yielded higher depression mean scores but nonetheless is categorized as minimal. Both groups have minimal depression levels and the t-test result confirms no significant difference in depression when grouped by lifestyle [t (67)=-.233, Sig=.817]. Findings suggest that depression is not based on having a sedentary or non-sedentary lifestyle.

The above result contrasts from Okely, Cukic, Shaw, Chastin, Dall, Deary , Der and Dontje's (2019) study that found that symptoms of depression was positively associated with sedentary time such that older adults who live a sedentary lifestyle would significantly differ in depressive symptoms compared to those with a non-sedentary lifestyle. The study may be explained by the fact that depressive symptoms may be explained by factors other than sedentary behaviors. For instance, Okely et al. (2019) highlighted the possible effect of sleep duration on depression. Buenaventura et al. (2020) emphasized the role of unmet spiritual needs, low moral support from at home, and reduced social interaction as factors that cause depressive symptoms. Huang et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of determining the form of sedentary behavior that older adults engaged in and categorized them into mentally passive and mentally active. Between the two, mentally passive sedentary behaviors led to greater depressive symptoms (Huang et al., 2020). In the current study, older adults were differentiated by lifestyle simply based on the number of hours they sit in a day. This categorization may prove to be a limitation of the study since some may be considered as sedentary with a mentally active behavior, whereas others may be considered as mentally passive but engage in non-sedentary behaviors. Further research therefore may explore other ways to categorize older adults' lifestyle to get a more detailed understanding of how lifestyles can influence depression and other mental health outcomes.

Table 6.

Differences in Level of Meaning in Life between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Meaning in Life	Lifestyle	t	df	Sig.
Presence of meaning	Sedentary	2.886	50.093	.006*
	Non-Sedentary			
Search for meaning	Sedentary	.061	67	.952
	Non-Sedentary			

*Significant at .05

The table above shows that there is a significant difference in presence of meaning [t (50.093)=2.886, Sig=.006] among older adults such that those with sedentary lifestyle have higher presence of meaning in life compared to their counterparts. According to Krause (2004), finding meaning

in the face of adversity is a challenging task necessitating profound introspection, imagination, determination and developed abstract reasoning. It may be inferred that those who spend time in sedentary behaviors, that is sitting, may still have engaged in active mental processes such as introspection, abstract reasoning and creativity leading them to develop higher presence of meaning compared to the non-sedentary older adults.

Moreover, Krause (2004) found that presence of meaning in life is associated with how an older adult copes with stress. Specifically, stressors affect older adults' health and in turn their sense of meaning. It can be inferred therefore that it is possible that those with sedentary behaviors cope with stressors comparatively better than those with non-sedentary lifestyles. Ryff and Singer (as cited in Krause (2004) however pointed out the bi-directional relationship of meaning in life and stress emphasizing how people with a greater sense of meaning, may enjoy better health and therefore may engage in more active behaviors enhancing their immune functioning.

From these, it is apparent that there is more to sedentary behaviors than just simply sitting. Palmer, Gray, Fitzsimons, Mutrie, Wyke, Deary,... & Skelton (2019) underscored this when they explored activities conducted by older adults when they are sitting and not sitting. They found that sitting activities may be divided into sitting activities done at home, and outside the home. Those that are done at home may involve watching TV, reading, doing puzzles, using computers or tablets, listening to talking books, playing a musical instrument, sitting thinking or doodling or sitting in the garden. Meanwhile, sitting behaviors done outside the home includes computer lessons, playing cards / board games, sitting in the park, going to the theater or cinema, or eating, drinking at cafes or restaurants (Palmer et al., 2019). Any of these activities may lead to a feeling of meaning in life; hence, it is critical that when exploring meaning in life among older adults, the nature of their sedentary behaviors has to be explored more in depth to gain more understanding of its nature.

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in search for meaning between older adults with sedentary and those with non-sedentary lifestyles [$t(67) = .061$, $Sig. = .952$]. Kim and Lee (2019) found that older adults, despite of cognitive and functional limitations, tend to search for meaning in their existence and attain a sense of joy in their current situations. This occurs regardless of whether the older adult engages in sedentary or non-sedentary behaviors since meaning in life is characteristically something that occurs as a function of age.

Table 7.

Differences in Level of Hope between Older Adults with Sedentary and Non-sedentary Lifestyles

Hope	Lifestyle	t	df	Sig.
Agency	Sedentary	2.578	45.230	.013*
	Non-Sedentary			
Pathway	Sedentary	1.785	67	.079
	Non-Sedentary			
Total Hope	Sedentary	1.286	67	.203
	Non-Sedentary			

*Significant at .05

T-test results above show that there is no significant difference in total hope when respondents are grouped by lifestyle [$t(67) = -1.286$, $Sig. = .203$] indicating that one's hopefulness will not vary depending on whether an older adult engages in sedentary or non-sedentary lifestyle. There is also no significant difference in pathway [$t(67) = -1.785$, $Sig. = .079$] by lifestyle. There is however a significant difference in agency when grouped by lifestyle [$t(45.230) = -2.578$, $Sig. = .013$] with higher scores being observed for those with a sedentary lifestyle.

Wroblewski and Snyder (2007) reported that higher hope indicates higher life satisfaction and increased perception of good physical health. Those with higher hope scores tend to believe that they can reach their goals, and they were moving in the direction of goal pursuits. Southerland (2012) added that having high hope is associated with enhanced decision-making. It can be inferred therefore that those living a sedentary lifestyle, in spite of the possible negative effects of their lifestyle on their physical health, engage in agentic thinking much more than those who live a non-sedentary lifestyle. These findings indicate that when health professionals or family members care for older adults, they must be mindful of these interpersonal characteristics so they may gain deeper understanding of their patient or relative and advocate for them appropriately.

Chapter 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

There is an increasing number of older adults aged 60 and above and it is expected to increase in the near future. This signals that efforts have to be placed on advocating for older adults welfare particularly that they remain prone to various issues not typically associated with normal aging such as depression. This study is Phase 2 of a research project that was designed to facilitate healthy aging among older adults. In this phase, older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles were compared in terms of depression, meaning in life and hope. Sedentary behavior was assessed based on the number of hours the older adult sat in a day, with 5 hours or more being considered as sedentary. Sixty-nine older adults were requested to participate by answering questionnaires. The Beck Depression Inventory – II, the Meaning in Life Questionnaire and the Adult Hope Scale were used to assess the main variables of the study.

Summary of Findings

1. Older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles both had minimal depressive symptoms.
2. Both groups of respondents had high presence of meaning and average search of meaning.
3. Older adults with sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles had high agency, pathways and overall hope in life.
4. There was no significant difference in depression, search of meaning in life, pathways and hope among sedentary and non-sedentary lifestyles. There was a significant difference in presence of meaning and agency with higher scores being observed among those with sedentary lifestyle.

Conclusions

1. Older adults, regardless of their lifestyle, coped well with their lives, and adjusted to their normal functioning after adversity.
2. Older adults who engage in sedentary and non-sedentary behaviors believed there is meaning in their lives and they actively seek out life's fulfillment and goals.
3. Sedentary and non-sedentary older adults had agentic thinking and know the pathway achieving their goals. They are generally hopeful and optimistic towards the future.
4. Sedentary behaviors did not create differences in one's tendencies towards depressive symptoms. Sedentary behaviors seemed to foster greater perceived meaning in life and agentic thinking possibly due to active mental processes that the older adults engage in.

Recommendations

1. Older adults, regardless of whether they engage in sedentary or non-sedentary lifestyles, will be advised to involve themselves in active mental activities such as reading, playing games and puzzles, writing and other cognitive demanding activities as these foster a greater perception of meaning in life and optimistic thinking.
2. Carers of older adults will be recommended to encourage or facilitate active physical and mental health of their elderly family member by promoting the older adults' engagement in active mental activities.
3. Local communities, government agencies and other organizations are recommended to create engaging activities amidst existing community quarantine guidelines that foster social connectedness, meaning in life and optimism among older adults.
4. Future research may explore further the nature of sedentary behaviors among older adults by discovering active and passive mental processes involved in this lifestyle.

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Appendices

Research Instruments

I. Please read the following items carefully. Answer the following items by placing a check (√) on the blanks provided on the statement that is true to you. (Mangyaring basahin ng mabuti ang mga sumusunod. Lagyan ng tsek (√) ang napiling sagot)

1. Name (optional)(*Pangalan*)(*Opsyonal*) _____
2. Sex (*Kasarian*) _____
3. Age(*Edad*) _____

BDI - II

1.	0	I do not feel sad (Ako ay hindi malungkot)
	1	I feel sad (Ako ay malungkot)
	2	I am sad all the time and I can't snap out of it (Ako ay madalas malungkot at mahina ang kakayanan para lampasan ito)
	3	I am so sad and unhappy that I can't stand it (Ako ay masyadong malungkot at hindi ko ito makakayanan)
2.	0	I am not particularly discouraged about the future (Hindi ako pinanghihinaan ng loob tungkol sa hinaharap)
	1	I feel discouraged about the future (Pinanghihinaan ako ng loob tungkol sa hinaharap)
	2	I feel I have nothing to look forward to (Pakiramdam ko ay wala akong inaasahan sa aking hinaharap)
	3	I feel the future is hopeless and that things cannot improve (Pakiramdam ko ay wala na akong pag-asa sa hinaharap at hindi na bubuti ang mga bagay sa aking buhay)
3.	0	I do not feel like a failure (Hindi ako naniniwalang ako ay isang bigo)
	1	I feel I have failed more than the average person (Pakiramdam ko ay mas bigo ako kaysa mga karamihan ng mga tao)
	2	As I look back on my life, all I can see is a lot of failures (Sa pagbabalik tanaw ko, wala akong ibang nakikita kundi ang napakarami kong kabiguan sa buhay)
	3	I feel I am a complete failure as a person (Pakiramdam ko ay isa akong malaking kabiguan)
4.	0	I get as much satisfaction out of things as I used to (Nakukuha ko ang aking kasiyahan sa mga bagay-bagay gaya ng dati)
	1	I don't enjoy things the way I used to (Hindi ako nageenjoy sa mga bagay na dati na sa aking buhay)
	2	I don't get real satisfaction out of anything anymore (Hindi ako nakakaramdam ng tunay na kasiyahan sa mga bagay-bagay)
	3	I am dissatisfied or bored with everything (Ako ay inip at wala ng kasiyahan sa lahat ng bagay)
5.	0	I don't feel particularly guilty (Hindi ako nagsisisi)
	1	I feel guilty a good part of the time (Ako bihirang magsisisi)
	2	I feel quite guilty most of the time (Ako laging ay nagsisisi)
	3	I feel guilty all of the time (Nagsisisi ako sa lahat ng panahon)
6.	0	I don't feel I am being punished (Hindi ako naniniwalang ako ay pinaparusahan)
	1	I feel I may be punished (Naniniwala akong ako'y paparusahan)
	2	I expect to be punished (Inaasahan kong ako ay mapaparusahan)
	3	I feel I am being punished (Naniniwala akong ako ay pinaparusahan)
7.	0	I don't feel disappointed in myself (Hindi ako dismayado sa aking sarili)

	1	I am disappointed in myself (Ako ay may pagkadismaya sa aking sarili)
	2	I am disgusted with myself (Ako ay naiinis sa aking sarili)
	3	I hate myself (Kinaiinisan ko ang aking sarili)
8.	0	I don't feel I am any worse than anybody else (Hindi ko nararamdaman na mas masama ako kupara sa ibang tao)
	1	I am critical of myself for my weaknesses or mistakes (Kritikal ako sa mga sarili kong kahinahan at pagkakamali)
	2	I blame myself all the time for my faults (Sinisisi ko ang aking sarili sa lahat ng aking pagkakamali)
	3	I blame myself for everything bad that happens (Sinisisi ko ang aking sarili sa lahat ng mga hindi magandang pangyayari)
9.	0	I don't have any thoughts of killing myself (Hindi ko iniisip na patayin ang aking sarili)
	1	I have thoughts of killing myself, but I would not carry them out (Iniisip ko na papatayin ang aking sarili pero hindi ko ito magagawa)
	2	I would like to kill myself (Gusto kong patayin ang aking sarili)
	3	I would kill myself if I had the chance (Papatayin ako ang aking sarili kung mabibigyan ako ng pagkakakataon)
10.	0	I don't cry any more than usual (Hindi na ako iiyak katulad ng dati)
	1	I cry more now than I used to (Mas umiiyak ako kaysa dati)
	2	I cry all the time now (Ngayon, umiiyak ako sa lahat ng oras)
	3	I used to cry, but now I can't cry even though I want to (Ngayon, hindi na ako makaiyak kahit gusto ko)
11.	0	I am no more irritated by things than I ever was (Hindi na ako naiinis sa mga bagay kumpara dati)
	1	I am slightly more irritated now than usual (Medyo naiinis ako ngayon kumpara dati)
	2	I am quite annoyed or irritated a good deal of the time (Medyo naiinis ako sa ilang pagkakataon)
	3	I feel irritated all the time (Naiinis ako sa lahat ng oras)
12.	0	I have not lost interest in other people (Hindi ako nawawalang ng interes sa ibang mga tao)
	1	I am less interested in other people than I used to be (Ako ay medyo hindi interesado sa ibang mga tao)
	2	I have lost most of my interest in other people (Nawala na karamihan ng interes ko sa ibang mga tao)
	3	I have lost all of my interest in other people (Nawala na lahat ng interes ko sa mga tao)
13.	0	I make decisions about as well as I ever could (Ako ay nagpapasya sa abot nga aking makakaya)
	1	I put off making decisions more than I used to (Hindi ako laging nagpapasya di gaya ng dati)
	2	I have greater difficulty in making decisions more than I used to (Nahihirapan ako ng sobra sa pagapasya di gaya ng dati)
	3	I can't make decisions at all anymore (Ngayon, hindi na ako nagpapasya sa lahat)
14.	0	I don't feel that I look any worse than I used to (Hindi ko nararamdaman na mas masahol ako kaysa dati)
	1	I am worried that I am looking old or unattractive (Nag-aalala ako na ako ay mukhang matanda at hindi na kaakitakit)
	2	I feel there are permanent changes in my appearance that make me look

		unattractive (Pakiramdam ko ay may permanenteng pagbabago sa aking hitsura na nagpapakitang hindi na ako kaakitakit)
	3	I believe that I look ugly (Naniniwala akong ako'y hindi maganda/gwapo)
15.	0	I can work about as well as before (Nakakatrabaho ako gaya ng dati)
	1	It takes an extra effort to get started at doing something (Kailangan ng dagdag na pagsisikap upang gawin ang isang bagay)
	2	I have to push myself very hard to do anything (Kailangan ko ng matinding pagganyak para gawin ang isang gawain)
	3	I can't do any work at all (Hindi ko kayang gawin ang lahat ng bagay)
16.	0	I can sleep as well as usual (Ako ay nakakatulog kagaya ng dati)
	1	I don't sleep as well as I used to (Hindi ako nakakatulog ng maayos kagaya ng dati)
	2	I wake up 1-2 hours earlier than usual and find it hard to get back to sleep (Nagigising ako ng isa hangang dalawang oras bago yung dating oras ng aking pagising)
	3	I wake up several hours earlier than I used to and cannot get back to sleep. (Nagigising ako ng ilang mga oras bago yung dating oras ng aking pagising at hindi na ako makatulog pa)
17.	0	I don't get more tired than usual (Ako ay hindi napapagod kagaya ng dati)
	1	I get tired more easily than I used to (Mas napapagod ako kumapara sa dati)
	2	I get tired from doing almost anything (Ako ay napapagod sa halos lahat ng ginagawa ko)
	3	I am too tired to do anything (Sobrang napapagod ako sa lahat ng ginagawa ko)
18.	0	My appetite is no worse than usual (Ang aking gana sa pagkain ay hindi masahol kagaya ng dati)
	1	My appetite is not as good as it used to be (Ang aking gana sa pagkain ay masahol kagaya ng dati)
	2	My appetite is much worse now (Ang aking walang gana sa pagkain ay lumalala na ngayon)
	3	I have no appetite at all anymore (Wala na akong gana sa pagkain ngayon)
19.	0	I haven't lost much weight, if any, lately (Hindi bumaba ang aking timbang kamakailan)
	1	I have lost more than five pounds (Bumaba ang aking timbang ng 5 Pounds)
	2	I have lost more than ten pounds (Bumaba ang aking timbang ng 10 Pounds)
	3	I have lost more than fifteen pounds (Bumaba ang aking timbang ng 15 Pounds)
20.	0	I am no more worried about my health than usual (Hindi na ako nagaalala tungkol sa aking timbang kaysa dati)
	1	I am worried about physical problems like aches, pains, upset stomach, or Constipation (Nagaalala ako tungkol pisikal na pananakit, pagkaligalig sa tyan, o paninigas ng dumi)
	2	I am very worried about physical problems and it's hard to think of much else (labis ako nagaalala tungkol sa mga pisikal na problema at nahahirapan ako dahil sa pagiisip ng marami pang iba)
	3	I am so worried about my physical problems that I cannot think of anything else (Wala na akong ibang iniisip kundi ang nagaalala tungkol sa mga pisikal na problema)
21.	0	I have not noticed any recent change in my interest in sex (Hindi ko napansin ang kamakailang pagbabago sa aking interes sa pakikipagtalik)
	1	I am less interested in sex than I used to be (Hindi ako gaanong interesado sa pakikipagtalik)
	2	I have almost no interest in sex (Halos wala na akong interes sa pakikipagtalik)
	3	I have lost interest in sex completely (Ako ay nawalan na ng interes sa

- _____6. I have discovered a satisfying life purpose. (Natuklasan ko ang kasiya-siyang layunin sa aking buhay)
- _____7. I am always searching for something that makes my life feel significant. (Palagi akong naghahanap ng kabuluhang mahalaga sa aking buhay)
- _____8. I am seeking a purpose or mission for my life. (Naghahanap ako ng makatuturang layunin o kaya'y misyon sa buhay)
- _____9. My life has no clear purpose. (Ang aking buhay ay walang makabuluhang layunin)
- _____10. I am searching for meaning in my life. (Hinahanap ko ang kabuluhan ng aking buhay)